

CREATING A NOTEPAD PROGRAM IN C++ BUILDER

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Abstract. This article describes the capabilities of C++Builder and its components. You can use C++Builder to develop the interface of the program you want to create. We will develop a blacknote program using this program.

Keywords: C++ Builder, Component Palette, The Code Editor, Caption, Run Time.

Introduction: First released in 1997, Borland C++ Builder is a Rapid Application Design environment that uses the C++ language, but includes the same GUI IDE as Borland Delphi. It includes the Delphi compiler and can make use of Delphi code in C++ projects. Borland C++ Builder replaces Borland C++ product. This product was targeted at business and enterprise customers. Current supported versions are sold by Embarcadero Technologies.

The Visual Component Library is the core set of objects C++Builder 6, offers to users on Microsoft Windows-based operating systems. This chapter describes features of the VCL framework and some frequently used components, while the next chapter presents advanced features and components in an attempt to enable readers to draw on the power of VCL in their Windows-based applications. Together, the two chapters cover most of the standard VCL functionality. However, specialized components like database access, Web services, and Internet components are reserved for later chapters where they are covered in depth. To enable developers to port their code between Windows-based operating systems and Linux, C++Builder 6 offers a separate set of components, called CLX, Component Library X-platform, which is the subject of another chapter. [1]

To start Borland C++ Builder, click Start _ Programs _ Borland C++ Builder 6_ C++ Builder 6.

Figure 1: C++Builder 6 environment

On the right side of the toolbars, there is a bar with multiple tabs; this is called the Component Palette.

Figure 2: The Component Palette.

The Component Palette holds many objects that you will be using to create your applications. The Component Palette, like a toolbar, can be moved to any location on the screen; but it is a good idea, if possible, to always keep it at its default location. The Component Palette is made of objects categorized in different tabs. To display a particular tab, click it.[2]

The Code Editor is featured text editor adapted for coding purposes. It is programmed to recognize the parts of a program that are recognized by C++ or not. To access the Code Editor, if you have a form opened, you can press F12. The Code Editor manages your jobs by organizing them into property pages (also called tabs). If your project contains more than one file, you can click the desired tab to access one of the files. The basic building block of a program is called a C++ file, and Borland calls it a Unit. Whenever you start Bcb, C++ Builder creates a starting project that has a C++ file called Unit1 while the project is called Project. Eventually, you will change these names to those you like. A typical code of a form, such as the one we have now, is built from at least two files: a header file and a source file. The file displaying now is called the source file; it gives direct instructions to the computer as to what to do on the form and why. The foundation of this source file (which is also the foundation of the form is in a file called the header file). By default, Bcb does not display this file at startup; you have to request it.[3]

Figure 3: The Code Editor

To create your applications, there are two settings you will be using. If a control is displaying on the screen and you are designing it, this is referred to as Design Time; this means that you have the ability to manipulate the control. You can visually control the control's appearance (its location), its size, and other necessary or available characters. The design view is usually the most used and the easiest because you can glance at what you see, have a realistic display of the control and configure its properties. The other system you will be using to control a window is with code, writing the program. This is done by typing commands or instructions using the keyboard.

This is considered or referred to as Run Time. This is the only way you can control an object's behavior while the user is interacting with the computer and your program. Even as the design and the run times provide the means of creating or testing your application, there are three ways you can add a control to a program. The visual design is the technique that allows you to visually add a control and manipulate its display. This is the most popular, the most regularly used,

and the easiest technique. Unfortunately, sometimes you will not be able to add a control when designing the application. Therefore, the other technique consists of creating a control using code.[4]

Figure 4: compilation window

Every control has a particular property as its default. This means that, when you visually add the control to a form or container, its default property is selected in the Object Inspector. If you start typing, that default property will receive your change. The default property of the form is the caption. The caption of a form is the word or group of words that display(s) on its title bar. Whenever you add a new form to your application, if you start typing, the Caption field in the Object Inspector would receive the change.[5]

```
//-----
void __fastcall TForm1::ChangingFormCaption()
{
Caption = "Today is " + Date();
}
//-----
```

We will create a notepad program using this program. The software part of this program is as follows:

```
//-----

#include <vcl.h>
#pragma hdrstop

#include "Unit1.h"
//-----
#pragma package(smart_init)
#pragma resource "*.dfm"
TForm1 *Form1;
String fn;
//-----

__fastcall TForm1::TForm1(TComponent* Owner)
: TForm(Owner)
```

```
{
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::yangi1Click(TObject *Sender)
{
    RichEdit1->Clear();
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::Yangisaqlash1Click(TObject *Sender)
{
    if(SaveDialog1->Execute())
    {
        RichEdit1->Lines->SaveToFile(SaveDialog1->FileName);
        fn=SaveDialog1->FileName;
        Form1->Caption = fn;
    }
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::ochish1Click(TObject *Sender)
{
    OpenFileDialog1->Execute();
    RichEdit1->Lines->LoadFromFile(OpenDialog1->FileName);
    fn = OpenFileDialog1->FileName;
    Form1->Caption = fn;
}
//-----

void __fastcall TForm1::saqlash1Click(TObject *Sender)
{
    if(fn.IsEmpty())
    {
        Yangisaqlash1->Click();
    }
    else
    {
        RichEdit1->Lines->SaveToFile(fn);
    }
}
//-----
```

The result of the program is as follows:

Figure 5: notepad programm window

Let's test the program by writing some text.

Figure 6: notepad programm window

In conclusion: With this program, you can write and save text data and open new windows. The File section has Save, Open in a new window, and Print sections.

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